

FABRICATION OF A ROTATING AND TILTING VICE

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Abstract

In this modern day there is evolving quest for competitive, safe, cost effective and high profit oriented machining solutions. At the same time, the job should be satisfy customer requirements. The drawbacks of earlier bench vise are overcome by the existing system. In the existing system, the radial drilling machine can be used to drill the fixed job with higher efficiency. But it cannot rotate or tilt the job to allow for drilling at other angular orientations. These drawbacks are overcome by this present design. Fabrication of the rotating and tilting machine vice can be operated without using mechanical linkage such as bevel gears and shafts as attempted by some researchers as they have their operational flaws. In this design, rotation motion is achieved by incorporating a frictionless bearing which permits seamless rotation of vice arrangement. The angular or tilting movement is provided by a metal hinge (fulcrum) which permits the tilting of the vice through 60° . Another unique design of this vice is that apart from the rotation of the entire vice assembly, the vice jaw can of its own rotate 360° to enable any job orientation on the machine. The proposed machine vice will be very useful to this generation and future generation of machine operators

Keywords: *Bench Vice, Rotating and Tilting vice, Drilling, cutting force*

Introduction

The need to ensure that one operator can conveniently operate the vice in a safe manner played a vital role in the design and fabrication of this rotating and tilting vice for drilling work which rotates without external and awkward mechanical link mechanisms like bevel gears, levers and shafts. In many of the previous designs of rotating vices, the rotation of the clamping jaws relied on link mechanisms of bevel gears and shafts attached externally beside and under the clamping table that makes it difficult for a single operator to operate and control his drilling activity safely and effectively. Cutting processes is one of the oldest and most common activities that predominantly takes place in the metalwork workshop and therefore, there is need for easy and effective clamping device that guarantee high productivity, easy handling and safety. This tilting and rotating vice is a modification that factions a rotating bearing right under the vice table which also carries the tilting mechanism. This makes rotating of the entire vice body easy to control, while carrying out the drilling or any other cutting activity without having to leave the vice to control rotating lever which the operator may need assistance from another operator to do so.

Cutting processes takes place by shearing of the material that is been shaped. There is gradual shearing of pieces of the material, called chips. The common cutting processes include shaping sawing, milling broaching, grinding drilling, and turning, etc. In all of these cutting operations, the basic mechanism is the same as it involve material removal to obtain the required shape and size, the difference is in the design and features of the cutting tool. The objective of the cutting process is to cut away the excess material and generate the desired shape and size.

However, one of the draw backs to achieving quick, accurate and cost effective cutting process is non-availability of cutting edge tools and accessories, which in most cases are very expensive to

acquire by some organizations in most developing countries. Therefore, it is imperative for the institutions to look inward so as to locally design and fabricate some of this equipment, and in some cases, the adaptable fixtures that may not be complex. One of such fixtures is a tilting and angle vice.

A vice is a tool used to hold or a workpiece firmly to allow operations such as cutting, filing, milling, drilling, grinding, etc. Vices are usually made from cast iron with a fixed jaw and another parallel jaw which moves towards or away from the fixed jaw that grips the workpiece against the fixed jaw (Chougule and Waghmare, 2015). The commonest vice in the engineering workshop is the bench vice, which is mounted to the top of the bench using bolts and nuts. This makes it rigidly fixed during operation. The lever of the lead screw operating the movable jaw enables the operator to easily move the workpiece if other sides of the workpiece have to be worked upon. Frequent tightening and un-tightening the jaws during operation is one of the limitations of the conventional bench vice, coupled with the fact that it is fixed to the work bench, making it impossible to be used elsewhere except on the workbench where it is fixed. Another limitation of conventional bench vice is that only drilling and cutting activities perpendicular to the vice can be done on it, it cannot permit cutting activities other angular surfaces. The only vice that is not fixed is the swivel-base vice which comes with the drilling or milling machine. This type of vice can rotate through 360 degree around its base, but is designed for the specific machine and not a general purpose vice that can be used for other cutting operations outside the machine where it is fitted.

The conventional bench vice has its fixed jaw connected to the workbench which does not allow it to move or rotate. In a bid to overcome these limitations, Chougule and Waghmare (2015) made a call for the design of a rigid, flexible, cost-effective and highly durable vice that will

consider the users' safety and comfort. To this end, some researchers have made successful efforts, and have designed and developed different types of vise to modify the existing ones for better productivity and operational convenience. Avdiu et al. (2012) designed a modified bench vice that using the morphological matrix method that have features like; self-locking, plastic jaw plate and swivel body, but it does not have any tilting mechanism for angular cutting. Sivasankaran (2017) in their study fabricated a machine vise with sliding link support with similar movements to a piston and connecting rod. In this vice, the cubic block will produces sliding action with the support of a rectangular plate between the movable jaw and the triangular piece. The same author and other researchers; Sivasankaran (2018), made an improvement of the his earlier design by producing another screw-less vice to overcome the frequent wear and tear of the lead screw; this was achieved by incorporating a dowel pin into the base block of the movable jaw. Furthermore, Hemachandran et al. (2020) designed a motor-operated vise that moves back and forth to hold the workpiece. It is worthy of note that all these designs were machine vices, and only adaptable to cutting on a particular machine. It was Chougule and Waghmare (2015) that designed a C-clamp with a plate at the top that can be attached to the base of the fixed jaw of a bench vice to allow changing the location of the bench vise The modification made it possible to raise the working position of the vise above the bench; by so doing, its productivity was enhanced. Makienko (1984) and Akanbi et al. (2020) in an empirical study found that the comfort of an operator using vise is related to the height of the vise above the ground. Kadam et al. (2016) successfully fabricated a rotating bench vice that could rotate in any direction on a horizontal plane; one part of the bottom is free to rotate, and the other part of the bottom is fixed to the bench.

A most recent study is the work of Rajendra Babu, et al (2019), which fabricated a rotating and tilting drilling vice whose rotation is provided by bevel gears and shafts. The limitations of the design are operational flaws; a single operator cannot effectively operate the lever to control the rotation and at the same time operate the vice jaws while machining.

Figure 1 Rotating and Tilting vice (Source: Rajendra Babu et al (2019))

This study is aimed at modifying the work of Rajendra, et al (2019) by incorporating frictionless bearing that allows the rotation of the entire vice assembly without the need for external gear and shaft arrangements. By this design, one single operator can conveniently control the rotation and tilting motions of the vice while performing the cutting activity. Another unique feature of this design is that apart from the rotation of the entire vice assembly, the clamping unit of the vice is also designed to rotate independently to allow for any job orientation. This intended design will eliminate the time spent by the operator to abandon his cutting activity to bend over in other to

operate the rotating lever. Another advantage of this design is that it permits tilting of the vice up to 60 degrees and it is easy to operate with less stress.

Design Methodology

This rotating vice is made up of the fixed and movable jaws forming the typical work clamping features which are made of cast iron. The screw handle, the screw and nut are made of mild steel. Each of the jaws has serrated steel plates fixed on them with dove tail screws that allows their replacement when they are worn out. The collar fixed at the end of slot acts as stopper to prevent the screw and the movable jaw from over-travelling and falling out. The rotating motion of the vice is provided by the frictionless ball bearing mounted under the base of the vice which seats on a 10mm steel plate. The bearing allows the operator to effortlessly swivel or rotate the entire vice assembly up to 360 degrees with one hand and at the same time control the drilling activity. The tilting mechanism consists of a perfectly milled angular slot mounted on the same mild steel base plate that carries the rotating bearing. A tilting lever crafted curved for easy handling operates on a screw to lock the vice when it is raised to any angle; the design allow tilting of vice between angle 0 – 60 degrees. Two technically fitted mild steel hinges form the fulcrum for the tilting of the vice arrangement. The fabricates rotating vice head is shown in figure 2

Figure 2 Fabricated rotating and tilting vice head

Major Parts of the Vice

The parts of the rotating vice include;

- The fixed jaw, movable jaws and lead screw
- The rotating base
- The tilting table
- The tilting slotted bracket
- The tilting locking lever and screw

Design Specifications

Axial clamping Force, F

The clamping force from the lead screw can be derived from the equation of the applied torque, T in equation 1.

$$T = \frac{Fdm}{2} \left[\frac{1+\pi dm}{2\pi dm - fl} \right] \dots \dots \dots 1$$

(Source: Mechanical engineering design 9th Edition, by Shigley)

Rearranging the equation 1 for the clamping force, F gives expression in equation 2.

$$F = \frac{2T}{dm} \left[\frac{\pi dm - fl}{1 + \pi dm} \right] \dots \dots \dots 2$$

Where F = the axial clamping force of the vice

T = applied torque at the turning lever (product of applied force and length of the lever)

dm = mean diameter of the power screw

f = frictional coefficient between the circular thread and the nut thread in the vice jaw

l = pitch of the lead screw

Materials and Fabrication

The materials for the rotating vice are basically cast iron for the vice jaws and body frame, and mild steel for the lead power screw, base plates and operating levers. The rotating and tilting vice machine was fabricated in the Metalwork Department Workshop, Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba, Delta State, using locally sourced materials. The fabricated vice is as shown in figure 3

Figure 3 Full picture of fabricated rotating and tilting vice

Results and Discussion

The fabricated rotating and tilting vice was tested in the workshop by using it to hold a workpiece while drilling and filing job were performed. The vice was tilted and drilling was effectively done at angle 56 degrees, and the vice was also rotated by the operator conveniently without leaving the drilling activity with one hand to operate external levers in order to achieve rotation. The extra time needed by the operator to leave the work on the machine and concentrate on the lever and bevel gears to rotate the work before coming to the vice have been eliminated as all the activities were done conveniently. The tilting mechanism mounted on the rotating base plate, all installed to rotate by a single bearing makes this vise unique, very convenient and cost effective. There is therefore, less fatigue and stress on the operator as there is no more bending over to operate the lever. There is better body balance and operational convenience.

Conclusion

Bench work is one of the commonest and versatile operations in the engineering machine workshop, and all the activities demand effective holding of the workpiece in a safe and convenient manner. The conventional bench vice by its design only holds work permanently on a fixed table and does not permit movement of the job in any other orientation while the machining operating is going on. For this reason, the rotating and tilting vice is fabricated to allow drilling and other operations to be done at angular surfaces. Existing rotating and tilting vices has limitation of operational difficulty as rotation was provided by external link mechanism of gears and shafts under and beside the vice table. Apart from the higher cost of this type of vice, it was almost impossible for a single operator to operate the rotation and tilting mechanism while controlling the drilling activity. This study; fabrication of a rotating and tilting vise modifies the

existing rotating vice by eliminating these limitations by building the entire vice table on a base plate mounted of a ball bearing. By the simple touch, the whole vice assemble can be rotated without the need of mechanical gears and shaft linkages. This enhances productivity, safety and operational comfort.

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